

THE USE OF AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS IN THE TEACHING STRATEGIES AMONG TEACHERS OF JOLO III DISTRICT, MINISTRY OF BASIC HIGHER, AND TECHNICAL EDUCATION – SULU

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ABSTRACT

This study is quantitative-descriptive research determining the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education – Sulu. Employing weighted mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent samples, one-way ANOVA, and Pearson's r test of correlation. The following are the findings of this study: 1) Out of 100 teacher-respondents, great majority are within 42 years old and above of age brackets, are female and most have 11-20 years length of service and with bachelor's degree. 2) Except for Subject delivery, all the Sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District in the context of pupil's engagement, pupil's output and pupil's behavioral attitude are all rated as "Agree" with total weighted mean score of 4.44, 4.36, 4.35 with standard deviation of .46608, .55403, and .53695 respectively by the teacher-respondents at Jolo III District. Additionally, sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District in the context of subject delivery is rated as "Strongly Agree" with total weighted mean score of 4.5443 with standard deviation of .46065 by the teacher-respondents at Jolo III District. 3) Generally, except for educational attainment, there is no significant difference in the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender, age, and length of service. Additionally, teacher-respondents differ in their perception towards the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of educational attainment. 4) Generally, the sub-categories subsumed the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among

teachers of Jolo III District is highly correlated which means there is but not strong interdependency among the subcategories subsumed.

Keywords: *Audiovisual materials, Teaching strategies, Subject Delivery, Pupils' Engagement, Pupils' Output, Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes.*

INTRODUCTION

As technology significantly changing the world, traditional teaching becomes lame and is undeniably ineffective. This is factual as even the learners of young ages are now equipped with technologies. The teachers in this modern world are then encouraged, if not mandated, to adapt to this technological evolution. The initiative of utilizing the technology in aiding the teaching process has been manifesting throughout the world.

Numerous global research studies demonstrate how teachers can improve the efficacy of the teaching and learning process by utilizing audiovisual tools. In reality, compared to traditional teaching methods, most students nowadays are more motivated to learn when audiovisual components are included. This was demonstrated in a study named "The Use of Audio-Visual Materials in Teaching and Learning Process in Effia Junior High Schools" conducted by Adwoa Kwegyiriba, Ronald Osei Mensah, and Elizabeth Ewusi (2022). They argue that although audio-visual resources are essential in Ghana's educational system, the results show that Effia's nine public JHSs lack proper instruction from their teachers on how to use these resources. Throughout their many educational experiences, the vast majority of students expressed a preference for audio-visual materials in their instruction, demonstrating their ongoing openness to learning using those resources. According to the report, educational stakeholders including the Ghana Education Service, the Ministry of Education, the Municipal Assembly, the Parent Teacher Association (P.T.A.), private funders, and non-governmental organizations should have access to audio-visual resources.

In the Philippines, the use of audiovisual materials is also prevalent throughout the country. Specifically in Laguna, according Coronado, Pascual & Orijala's (2021) a study. The free internet apps that connect them to the outside world are an additional addition to them. These methods of learning have even been introduced into the classroom, where they are widely regarded as an integral element of the environment for students in the twenty-first century. In order to provide lessons to children of all ages, audio-visual equipment has been essential from kindergarten through primary school.

The use of audio-visual materials is essential to Ghana's educational system; however, students in the nine public JHS in Effia are not receiving an adequate education from their teachers when they use these resources, as found by Osei et. al. (2022). Throughout their diverse classroom experiences, the majority of students indicated that they preferred to be taught using audio-visual materials, demonstrating their ongoing readiness to receive instruction using those tools. The study suggests that educational stakeholders, including the Ghana Education Service, the Ministry of Education, the

Municipal Assembly, the Parent Teacher Association (P.T.A.), private funders, and non-governmental organizations, should have access to audio-visual materials.

Song & Zhang (2018) audiovisual materials would provide a better learning environment, creating more opportunities for conversation, and help students construct their learning system more effectively. Thus, every school should provide audiovisual materials to enhance the teaching and learning process for the betterment of students' learning.

Today's students are familiar with contemporary technology. The free internet apps that connect them to the outside world are an additional addition to them. These methods of learning have even been introduced into the classroom, where they are widely regarded as an integral element of the environment for students in the twenty-first century. Audio-visual equipment has been an essential instrument for teaching lessons to children of all ages, from kindergarten to elementary school (Coronado, Pascual & Orijala, 2021).

In Sulu, the acknowledgment of the technologies by the young learners are also rampant. This is questioning the effectiveness of traditional teaching by the perennial educators, thus the urge to engage technology in their classrooms. The researcher then yearns to study the effects of technology, specifically the audiovisual materials, to the teaching process among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu.

Research Questions:

Specifically, this answered to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education – Sulu in terms of:
 - 1.1. Gender;
 - 1.2. Age;
 - 1.3. Length of Service; and
 - 1.4. Educational Attainment?
2. What is the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education – Sulu as to:
 - 2.1. Subject Delivery;
 - 2.2. Pupils' Engagement;
 - 2.3. Pupils' Output; and
 - 2.4. Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes?
3. Is there a significant difference on the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education – Sulu when they are grouped according to their:
 - 3.1. Gender;
 - 3.2. Age;
 - 3.3. Length of Service; and

- 3.4. Educational Attainment?
4. Is there a significant correlation among the variables subsumed under the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education – Sulu as to:
 - 4.1. Subject Delivery;
 - 4.2. Pupils' Engagement;
 - 4.3. Pupils' Output; and
 - 4.4. Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A quantitative-descriptive research design was employed to ascertain the degree to which one hundred (100) teachers from the Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technological Education – Sulu's Jolo III District used audiovisual materials as part of their teaching strategies in order to achieve the comprehensive research layout for the data collection in this study.

Research Locale

This research study was conducted at the seven (7) selected public elementary schools of Jolo III District, specifically; Lawm Alat Elementary School, Bakud Central Elementary School, Jati Elementary School, Asturias Elementary School, Tanjung Elementary School, Camp Asturias Elementary School, and Kasanyangan Elementary School.

Respondents of the Study

The target respondents of this study was the one hundred (100) selected teachers of Jolo III District, Division of Sulu from seven (7) different schools during the school year 2023-2024. They were either Male or Female, single or married, so long as they were teaching during the period of the study was conducted.

Table 1. Shows the list of the seven (7) target Public Schools of Jolo III District.

Jolo III District, Division of Sulu	Number of Respondents
Lawm Alat Elementary School	20
Bakud Elementary School	20
Jati Elementary School	20
Asturias Elementary School	10
Tanjung Elementary School	10
Camp Asturias Elementary School	10
Kasanyangan Elementary School	10
Total	100

Sampling Design

This study used a purposive sampling strategy. Units are chosen for inclusion in the sample using this non-probability sampling technique based on factors including geographic closeness, availability at a specific time, or willingness to participate in the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

To collect the data, the researcher employed the survey instrument after being validated. Permission to administer the said instrument is sought from the Dean of Graduate Studies of Sulu State College, the Sulu Division Office Superintendent, and the Supervisor of Jolo III District, as well as the Principal or Teacher-in-charge of the target seven (7) Schools from Jolo III District. Subsequently, the researcher launched and retrieved the said instrument personally.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire was used to gather data on the extent of The Use of Audiovisual Materials in the Teaching Strategies among Teachers of Jolo III District. This instrument was adapted with minor modification, took from standardized questionnaires of Bukidnon State University on The Practices of Public Elementary School Teachers on the 21st Century Skills: Basis for Intervention, also from research for CSS 12 students of DJPRSHS to discover the Effects/Impact of Modern Technology in Students' academic performance which is posted on scribd.com by Jhon Batuigas(2019). Additionally, a survey study by George, Adekunle Pius, and Ige Nelson Adewole (2022) on pre-service teachers' use of audio-visual resources in Lagos State Colleges of Education is published in the Academic Research Journal of Psychology and Counselling.

The instrument employed in this study was divided into two parts: Part I of the questionnaire asked questions about the respondents' age, gender, length of service, and Education Attainment. In Part II, the extent to which Jolo III District teachers used audiovisual materials in their lesson plans was assessed in terms of Subject delivery, Pupils' Engagement, Pupils' Output, and Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive and inferential statistical tools was appropriately employed in the treatment of data to be gathered for this study, namely:

1. For research number one (1), the frequency and percentage were the statistical tools used to determine the profile of the teachers as to gender, age, length of service, educational attainment.

2. For research question number two (2), the weighted mean and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among Teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education – Sulu enrolled during the school year 2023-2024.

3. For research question number three (3), t-test and one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used. t-test for independent variable was employed to determine the significant differences of The Use of Audiovisual Materials in the Teaching Strategies among Teachers of Jolo III District Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education – Sulu when data are grouped according gender, However, when data are grouped based on age, length of service, and educational level, one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to identify the significant differences.

4. For question number four (4), The teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education - Sulu, employed Pearson Product-Moment Correlation to ascertain the significant correlation between the sub-categories covered under the extent of using audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies with respect to subject delivery, pupil’s engagement, pupils output, and pupil’s behavioral attitudes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. What is the demographic profile of the teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu in terms of: 1.1 Gender, 1.2 Age, 1.3 Length of Service; and 1.4 Educational Attainment?

1.1 In terms of Gender

Table 1.1 shows the demographic profile of teacher-respondents in terms of gender. This table indicates that, of the 100 teacher respondents, 9 (9.0%) are men and 91 (91.0%) are women. According to this study, there are more female than male among the overall number of teachers-respondent. This suggests that female make up the vast majority of the teacher-respondent from the Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education - Sulu's Jolo III District.

Table 1.1 Demographic profile in terms of gender.

Gender	Number of respondents	Percent
Male	9	9.0%
Female	91	91.0%
Total	100	100%

1.2 In terms of Age

Table 1.2 illustrates the age-related demographic profile of the teacher responders. The following table illustrates that, out of the 100 teacher responders, 7 (7.0%) are younger than 25, 29 (29.0%) are between 26 and 31 years old, 31 (31.0%) are between 32 and 41 years old, and 33 (33.0%) are retired. The results of this study show that about one-third of the instructor respondents are 42 years of age or older. This indicates even further that most of the teachers who participated in this survey are in the upper age group according to the study's definition.

Table 1.2 Demographic profile in terms in terms of age.

Age	Number of respondents	Percent
25 years old and below	7	7.0%
26-31 years old	29	29.0%
32-41 years old	31	31.0%
42 years old and above	33	33.0%
Total	100	100%

1.3 In terms of Length of service

Table 1.3 demonstrates the teacher respondents' demographic profile according to their years of service. The table revealed that, of the 100 teacher respondents, 28 (28.0%) had been in the field for less than five years, 27 (27.0%) for six to ten years, 29 (29.0%) for eleven to fifteen years, 15 (15.0%) for twenty-one to forty years, and 1 (1.0%) for forty years or more. Nearly one-third of the teacher responders in this study have been employed there for between eleven and twenty years. This implies that there are a significant number of mid-career professors in the Omar District.

Table 1.3 Demographic profile in terms of length of service.

Length of service	Number of respondents	Percent
5 years and below	28	28.0%
6 to 10 years	27	27.0%
11 to 20 years	29	29.0%
21-40 years	15	15.0%
41 years and above	1	1.0%
Total	100	100%

1.4 In terms of Educational Attainment

Table 1.4 demonstrates the educational attainment of the instructor respondents' demographic profile. Based on the data shown in this table, 86 (86.0%) of the 100 teacher respondents have a bachelor's degree, 12 (12.0%) have a bachelor's degree with master's units, 2 (2.0%) have a master's degree, and none have a doctorate. More than half of all teacher respondents, according to this study, only hold a bachelor's degree. This implies that the prevalence of bachelor's degrees among the teacher-respondents involved in this study suggest a need for an ongoing professional development and opportunities for career advancement among the elementary school teachers of Omar District.

Table 1.4 Demographic profile in terms of educational attainment.

Educational Attainment	Number of respondents	Percent
Bachelor's Degree	38	38.0%
Bachelor's degree with Master's units	34	34.0%
Master's degree	21	21.0%
Master's degree with Doctorate units	6	6.0%
Doctorate Degree	1	1.0%
Total	100	100%

2. What is the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu as to: 2.1 Subject Delivery, 2.2 Pupils' Engagement, 2.3 Pupils' Output; and 2.4 Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes?

2.1 In the context of Subject Delivery

Table 2.1 shows the extent of the use of audiovisual in the context of Subject Delivery. With a weighted mean score of 4.54 overall and a standard deviation of .46065, this category was rated as "Strongly Agree". This result implies that the teachers who took part in the study strongly agreed about the degree to which instructional strategies involving audiovisual resources are applied within the framework of topic delivery. This implies that teachers see audiovisual materials as helpful instruments to encourage learning and student participation.

Notably, teacher-respondents rated the following items as "**Strongly Agree**": "Pupils understand the teacher when images or videos are shown", "Pupils follow the instructions easily when the teacher shows images or videos.", "I believe instructions were

clearly provided when Audiovisual Materials were used.”, and “Use of Audiovisual materials help pupil’s actual atmosphere of learning.”

Table 2.1 Extent of the use of audiovisual in the context of Subject Delivery.

Statements	Mean	S.D	Rating
1 Pupils understand the teacher when images or videos are shown.	4.77	.446	Strongly Agree
2 Pupils follow the instructions easily when the teacher shows images or videos.	4.59	.570	Strongly Agree
3 I believe instructions were clearly provided when Audiovisual Materials were used.	4.50	.628	Strongly Agree
4 Use of Audiovisual materials help pupil’s actual atmosphere of learning.	4.57	.590	Strongly Agree
5 Use of Audiovisual materials provide realistic experience for learners.	4.47	.611	Agree
6 Brainstorm and seek out knowledge for pupils to improve their ideas on the particular subject.	4.44	.671	Agree
7 Bring together relevant information and perspectives for pupils.	4.47	.643	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.54	.46065	Strongly Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Undecided; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

2.2 In the context of Pupils’ Engagement

Table 2.2 shows the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the context of Pupils’ Engagement. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of **4.44** with standard deviation of **.46608** which is rated as “Agree”. This result indicates that the teachers involved in this study affirmed that generally agree with the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in teaching strategies within the context of Pupils’ Engagement. This implies that Teachers recognize the value of audiovisual materials in capturing students' interest and fostering active participation, leading to a more engaging classroom environment.

Notably, teacher-respondents rated the following items, among others as “**Agree**”: “I found the audiovisual materials more engaging.”, “Audiovisual materials helped pupils to collaborate and cooperate with group activities.”, “Pupils participate actively in discussions.”, “Participate in accessing information in an effective manner which is related to the pupils’ learning.” and, “Motivates students to get more involved in learning activities.”

Table 2.2 Extent of the use of audiovisual in the context of Pupils' Engagement.

	Statements	Mean	S. D	Rating
1	Pupils are enjoy when I use Audiovisual Materials.	4.68	.469	Strongly Agree
2	I found the audiovisual materials more engaging.	4.39	.680	Agree
3	Audiovisual materials helped pupils to collaborate and cooperate with group activities.	4.43	.590	Agree
4	Pupils participate actively in discusssions.	4.38	.582	Agree
5	Create collaborative group activities to encourage participation.	4.42	.572	Agree
6	Participate in accessing information in an effective manner which is related to the pupils' learning.	4.34	.639	Agree
7	Motivates students to get more involved in learning activities.	4.47	.594	Agree
	Total Weighted Mean	4.44	.46608	Agree

2.3 In the context of Pupils' Output

Table 2.3 shows the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the context of Pupils' Output. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.36 with standard deviation of .55403 which is rated as "Agree". This result indicates that the teachers involved in this study affirmed that they generally agree with the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in teaching strategies within the context of Pupils' Output. Furthermore, this implies that Teachers recognize the value of audiovisual materials in stimulating students' creativity, facilitating active participation, and promoting meaningful learning experiences that contribute to higher-quality output.

Notably, teacher-respondents rated the following items, among others as "**Agree**": "I believe audiovisual materials are a good way to assess students' understanding of a topic.", "The Pupils answer more accurately the question when Audiovisual materials are used.", "When Audiovisual materials are used, the pupils can express their idea and creativity more effectively.", "Pupils do the tasks better (e.g. seatwork, short quiz, and assignment) when the teachers show images and videos." and, "Audiovisual materials increase academic achievement more than traditional method."

Table 2.3 Extent of the use of audiovisual in the context of Pupils' Output.

Statements	Mean	S. D	Rating
1 Audiovisual materials helped the pupils to exercise their creativity.	4.54	.558	Strongly Agree
2 I believe audiovisual materials are a good way to assess students' understanding of a topic.	4.36	.704	Agree
3 The Pupils answer more accurately the question when Audiovisual materials are used.	4.26	.691	Agree
4 When Audiovisual materials are used, the pupils can express their idea and creativity more effectively.	4.31	.662	Agree
5 Audiovisual materials enhance pupils' communication skills.	4.34	.699	Agree
6 Pupils do the tasks better (e.g. seatwork, short quiz, and assignment) when the teachers show images and videos.	4.38	.722	Agree
7 Audiovisual materials increase academic achievement more than traditional method.	4.32	.723	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.36	.55403	Agree

2.4 In the context of Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes

Table 2.4 shows the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the context of Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.35 with standard deviation of .53695 which is rated as "Agree". This result indicates that that teachers in Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education – Sulu generally agree with the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in teaching strategies within the context of Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes. Furthermore, this implies that Teachers perceive audiovisual materials as effective tools for promoting positive attitudes and behaviors among students, such as attentiveness, enthusiasm for learning, and active participation in classroom activities.

Notably, teacher-respondents rated the following items, among others as "**Agree**": "Pupils ask questions to get more information when audivisual materials are used.", "Raises his/her hand to answer a question or volunteer information when audiovisual materials are used.", "Use of Audivisual helps Pupils pronounce accurately the word.", "Use of audiovisual materials help pupils enhance retention memory." and, "The use of audiovisual aids make the students to remember the concept for longer period of time."

Table 2.4 Extent of the use of audiovisual in the context of Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes

	Statements	Mean	S. D	Rating
1	Pupils ask questions to get more information when audivisual materials are used.	4.29	.671	Agree
2	Raises his/her hand to answer a question or volunteer information when audiovisual materials are used.	4.29	.743	Agree
3	Pupils pay attention in class.	4.50	.659	Strongly Agree
4	Use of Audivisual helps Pupils pronounce accurately the word.	4.27	.664	Agree
5	Use of audiovisual materials help pupils enhance retention memory.	4.39	.665	Agree
6	The use of Audivisual materials support activities that facilitate higher-order thinking (e.g. collaborative activities, that require analysis of information)	4.38	.599	Agree
7	The use of audiovisual aids make the students to remember the concept for longer period of time.	4.32	.680	Agree
	Total Weighted Mean	4.35	.53695	Agree

3. Is there a significant difference on the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu when they are grouped according to their: 3.1 Gender, 3.2 Age, 3.3 Length of Service; and 3.4 Educational Attainment?

3.1 According to Gender

Table 3.1 presents the difference the extent of the use of audiovisual materials when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender. All of the t-values and probability values are not significant at alpha 0.05, as this table illustrates. This indicates that the perceptions of the male and female teacher respondents in this study regarding the subcategories covered by the degree to which teachers in the Jolo III use audiovisual materials in their teaching strategies do not differ. This suggests further that, as a male teacher-respondent, he may be more perceptive of the amount to which instructors in the Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education - Sulu, use audiovisual resources in their lesson plans, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable gender has no significant intervention in the ways how teacher-respondents at Jolo III District perceive the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that: "There is no significant difference in the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic, Higher, and Technical Education – Sulu, when data are classified according to their demographic profile in terms of gender" is accepted.

Table 3.1 Difference in the extent of the use of audiovisual in terms of gender.

Variables	Grouping	Mean	S.D	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description																												
Subject Delivery	Male	4.5238	.37796	-.02250	-.1390	.890	Not Significant																												
	Female	4.5463	.46976					Pupils' Engagement	Male	4.5238	.44607	.08739	.16345	.594	<i>Not Significant</i>	Female	4.4364	.46965	Pupils' Output	Male	4.2063	.72882	-.16728	.19384	.390	Not Significant	Female	4.3736	.53654	Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes	Male	4.3492	.44671	.00070	.18858
Pupils' Engagement	Male	4.5238	.44607	.08739	.16345	.594	<i>Not Significant</i>																												
	Female	4.4364	.46965					Pupils' Output	Male	4.2063	.72882	-.16728	.19384	.390	Not Significant	Female	4.3736	.53654	Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes	Male	4.3492	.44671	.00070	.18858	.997	Not Significant	Female	4.3485	.54719						
Pupils' Output	Male	4.2063	.72882	-.16728	.19384	.390	Not Significant																												
	Female	4.3736	.53654					Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes	Male	4.3492	.44671	.00070	.18858	.997	Not Significant	Female	4.3485	.54719																	
Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes	Male	4.3492	.44671	.00070	.18858	.997	Not Significant																												
	Female	4.3485	.54719																																

* Significant at alpha 0.05

3.2 According to Age

Table 3.2 presents the difference in the extent of the use of audiovisual materials when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age. This table indicates that all of the F-values and probability values of the subcategories that are included are not significant at alpha 0.05, with the exception of the student's output. This indicates that, despite age differences among the teacher respondents, there is generally no difference in the way that teachers in Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education - Sulu, perceive the subcategories that fall under the umbrella of the extent to which audiovisual materials are used in their teaching strategies. This further suggests that, in comparison to teacher respondents between the ages of 25 and 42, teachers in the Jolo III District of the Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education - Sulu may not have a better perception of the extent to which these materials are used in their teaching strategies.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable age has no significant intervention in the ways how teacher-respondents at Jolo III District perceive the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that: “There is no significant difference in the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu, when data are classified according to their demographic profile in terms of age” is accepted.

Table 3.2 Difference in the extent of the use of audiovisual in terms of age.

Sources of Variation		Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Subject Delivery	Between Groups	.855	3	.285	1.358	.260	Not Significant
	Within Groups	20.153	96	.210			
	Total	21.008	99				
Pupils' Engagement	Between Groups	1.507	3	.502	2.411	.072	Not Significant
	Within Groups	19.999	96	.208			
	Total	21.506	99				
Pupils' Output	Between Groups	2.797	3	.932	3.245	.025	Significant
	Within Groups	27.590	96	.287			
	Total	30.388	99				
Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes	Between Groups	1.446	3	.482	1.708	.170	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.097	96	.282			
	Total	28.544	99				

3.3 According to Length of service

Table 3.3 presents the difference the extent of the use of audiovisual materials when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of length of service. This table indicates that, at alpha 0.05, none of the F-values or probability values for the subcategories that are included are significant. This indicates that even though the teacher respondents in this study have varying lengths of service, they generally have similar perceptions about how much the teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu, use audiovisual materials in their lesson plans. It suggests that compared to those who have only had five years or less, teacher-respondents who have been employed for 41 years or more may not be better able to gauge the level of parental involvement in public school programs and activities at Omar District, Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education – Sulu.

Hence, it is safe to say that the length of service variable has no significant intervention in the ways how teacher-respondents perceive the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that: “There is no significant difference in the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu, when data are classified according to their demographic profile in terms of length of service” is accepted.

Table 3.3 Difference in the extent of the use of audiovisual in terms of length of service.

Sources of Variation		Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Subject Delivery	Between Groups	.767	4	.192	.900	.467	Not Significant
	Within Groups	20.241	95	.213			
	Total	21.008	99				
Pupils' Engagement	Between Groups	1.026	4	.257	1.190	.320	Not Significant
	Within Groups	20.480	95	.216			
	Total	21.506	99				
Pupils' Output	Between Groups	1.507	4	.377	1.239	.300	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.881	95	.304			
	Total	30.388	99				
Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes	Between Groups	1.373	4	.343	1.200	.316	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.170	95	.286			
	Total	28.544	99				

* Significant at alpha 0.05

3.4 According to Educational Attainment

Table 3.4 presents the difference the extent of the use of audiovisual materials when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of educational attainment. This table shows that all of the F-values and probability values of the subcategories covered by the degree to which teachers of the Jolo III District use audiovisual materials in their teaching strategies, are significant at alpha 0.05, with the exception of subject delivery and student engagement. This indicates that while the educational backgrounds of the teacher-respondents in this study vary, they generally have different opinions about how much parental involvement there should be in public school activities and programs at Omar District, Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education – Sulu. It suggests that master's degree-holding teacher responders would

have a superior understanding of the level of parental involvement in public school programs and activities, at Omar District, Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education – Sulu compared to those who only have bachelor’s degree, and vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that the educational attainment variable has indeed significant intervention in the ways how teacher-respondents perceive the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that: “There is no significant difference in the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu, when data are classified according to their demographic profile in terms of educational attainment” is rejected.

Table 3.4 Difference in the extent of the use of audiovisual in terms of Educational Attainment.

Sources of Variation		Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Subject Delivery	Between Groups	1.973	4	.546	2.686	.051	Not Significant
	Within Groups	19.035	95	.200			
	Total	21.008	99				
Pupils' Engagement	Between Groups	2.185	4	.546	2.686	.051	Not Significant
	Within Groups	19.321	95	.203			
	Total	21.506	99				
Pupils' Output	Between Groups	3.648	4	.912	3.240	.015	Significant
	Within Groups	26.740	95	.281			
	Total	30.388	99				
Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes	Between Groups	3.746	4	.937	3.588	.009	Significant
	Within Groups	24.798	95	.261			
	Total	28.544	99				

The extent to which teachers in the Jolo III District of the Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education - Sulu use audiovisual materials in their teaching strategies varies among the groups classified according to Educational Attainment was determined by a Post Hoc Analysis using the Tukey test. This analysis was done after the data were grouped according to the demographic profile of the students who responded in terms of Educational Attainment.

On Pupils' Output: It shows that teacher-respondents who have Master with doctoral units obtained the mean difference of **1.04762*** with Standard Error of .37515 and p-value of .049 which is significant at alpha 0.05 over teacher-respondents who have Doctorate degree in their educational attainment. This indicates a significant difference in perception between teacher-respondents who have completed master's degrees with doctoral units and those who have obtained Doctorate degrees towards the extent of extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu. It implies that teacher-respondents with master's degrees and doctoral units perceive better towards the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu compared to those with Doctorate degrees. This could imply that additional coursework or training beyond the master's level may have practical implications for teaching effectiveness in certain contexts.

On Pupils' Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes: It shows that teacher-respondents who have Master with doctoral units obtained the mean difference of **.66792*** with Standard Error of .22444 and p-value of .030 which is significant at alpha 0.05 over teacher-respondents who have bachelor's degree in their educational attainment. This indicates a significant difference in perception between teacher-respondents who have completed master's degrees with doctoral units and those who have obtained Doctorate degrees towards the extent of extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu. It implies that teacher-respondents with master's degrees and doctoral units perceive better towards the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District compared to those with bachelor's degrees. This could imply that advanced education and training have practical implications for creating a positive and supportive classroom environment conducive to fostering desirable behavioral attitudes among students.

Table 3.3.1 Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in the extent of the use of audiovisual in terms of Educational Attainment.

Dependent Variable	(I) Grouping by Educational Attainment	(J) Grouping Educational Attainment	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
		Bachelor's degree	.62406	.23306	.065
Pupils' Output:	Master with doctoral units	Bachelor's degree with Master units	.36364	.23546	.537
		Master full pledged	.55000	.24695	.179

			1.04762*	.37515	.049
Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes	Master with doctoral units	Doctorate degree Bachelor's degree	.66792*	.22444	.030
		Bachelor's degree with Master units	.35714	.22675	.517
		Master full pledged	.43333	.23782	.367
		Doctorate degree	.88095	.36127	.114

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

4. Is there a significant correlation among the variables subsumed under the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu?

Table 4 shows the correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu. As shown in the table, the computed Pearson correlation Coefficients (Pearson r) between these variables are significant at alpha 0.05.

Furthermore, the correlational degree among the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu is as follows:

- 1) Very High positive degree of correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District.

Strong correlation among all subcategories implies that the use of audiovisual materials is consistently and uniformly perceived by the teacher-respondents involved in this study as beneficial across various aspects of teaching strategies. This implies that incorporating audiovisual resources can enhance multiple facets of teaching, including subject delivery, pupil engagement, pupils' output, and behavioral attitudes.

Hence, it is safe to say that generally the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu are highly correlated. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the use of audiovisual materials

in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu” is rejected.

Table 4 shows the correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the use of audiovisual materials in the teaching strategies among teachers of Jolo III District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education – Sulu.

Variables		Pearson <i>r</i>	Sig.	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Subject Delivery	Pupils' Engagement	.785**	.000	100	Very High
	Pupils' Output	.735**	.000	100	Very High
	Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes	.743**	.000	100	Very High
Pupils' Engagement	Pupils' Output	.753**	.000	100	Very High
	Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes	.783**	.000	100	Very High
Pupils' Output	Pupils' Behavioral Attitudes	.766**	.000	100	Very High

*Correlation coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002):

0.0-0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.3 = Low; 0.3-0.5 = Moderate; 0.5-0.7 = High; 0.7-0.9 = Very High; 0.9-1 = Nearly Perfect.

Conclusions

The study concludes the following:

1) The demographic profile of teacher-respondents in the Jolo III District is characterized by a predominance of females. Additionally, a substantial majority falls within the age group of 42 years old and above of age brackets. Furthermore, majority of teacher-respondents have moderate to significant experience in the education sector and holds bachelor's degree.

2) This study concludes drawn from this result is that teacher-respondents at Jolo III District overwhelmingly agree on the effectiveness and importance of integrating audiovisual materials into teaching strategies across various aspects of education, particularly in the context of pupil engagement, output, and behavioral attitude. underscores the importance of continued support and investment in audiovisual resources, professional development initiatives, and instructional practices aimed at

maximizing the potential of audiovisual materials to enrich teaching and learning in Jolo III District.

3) Generally, the extent of the use of audiovisual materials across gender, age, and length of service suggests that factors such as gender, age, and years of service do not significantly influence teachers' utilization of audiovisual resources in teaching strategies. This indicates a consistent approach to incorporating audiovisual materials among teachers regardless of demographic characteristics. In contrast, the significant difference in perception based on educational attainment suggests that teachers with different levels of educational attainment have varying perspectives on the use of audiovisual materials. This highlights the potential influence of educational background on teachers' attitudes and beliefs regarding the effectiveness or importance of audiovisual resources in teaching strategies.

4) Generally, a very high degree of correlation concludes that changes or variations in one sub-category may be accompanied by changes in another sub-category, reflecting a degree of coherence or consistency in teachers' perceptions or practices related to the use of audiovisual materials.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

- 1) Department of Education (DepEd) may allocate resources for the acquisition, development, and maintenance of audiovisual materials and technology infrastructure in schools. This includes investing in modern audiovisual equipment, educational software, and digital resources to ensure teachers have access to up-to-date materials for teaching.
- 2) Jolo III District faculty members are encouraged to experiment with different types of audiovisual materials and innovative teaching strategies to determine what works best for their students. This can involve exploring new technologies, multimedia resources, and instructional approaches to create engaging and interactive learning experiences.
- 3) Faculty members may collaborate with colleagues across all districts in Sulu province, share best practices, and exchange ideas for using audiovisual materials in teaching. This can be facilitated through professional learning communities, online forums, and peer mentoring programs to foster a culture of collaboration and continuous improvement.
- 4) More so, Future researchers in the field of Education are encouraged to include comparative studies to compare the effectiveness of different types of audiovisual materials, teaching strategies, and instructional approaches across different contexts and settings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

First and foremost, each participant received a detailed informed consent form outlining the trial's objectives, procedures, possible risks and benefits, and confidentiality policies. In addition, all trial data points were meticulously anonymized when the respondents' personal information had no bearing on the trial's outcomes. Data collection

was carried out in a private setting to protect participant privacy, and the collected data was stored in a secure archive that was only accessible by the researchers. All participants were treated with respect, regardless of differences in opinions and points of view.

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